

FortScript: A Transpiler Targeting Modern, Parallel, Scalable Fortran

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Abstract

Traditionally, libraries like OpenMP [1] and MPI [2] have been used for developing parallel HPC applications with Fortran [3]. Modern Fortran standards (2008 [4], 2018 [5], 2023 [6]) have introduced additional language features meant to support both loop-level parallelism and scalable Single Program Multiple Data (SPMD) parallelism natively. FortScript, implemented in OCaml, provides a Python-like Domain-Specific Language (DSL) for scientific computing that transpiles to Fortran. FortScript is the first such transpiler to take advantage of modern Fortran loop-level and SPMD parallelism language features on single-node and distributed CPUs. The software makes modern parallel Fortran more accessible to HPC application developers.

Keywords: Python, Fortran, Coarrays, Parallelism, Distributed Computing, Simulation

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1 Highlights

- Transpiler for a Python-like domain specific language to modern parallel Fortran.
- Takes advantage of Fortran’s built-in loop-level (including GPU offload) and coarray parallelism.
- Comes with a partially bootstrapped support library for plotting, HDF5 I/O, Finite Volume Method, and more.

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2 Introduction

Several notable Python-Fortran transpilers have been written in the past. The transpyle [7, 8] project was last updated eight years ago to generate C and Fortran 95 code, with the code generation, AST, etc. written in Python. The pyccl [9] project, which is actively maintained, generates both C and Fortran code from a variant of Python, but does not take advantage of modern Fortran parallelism features. A popular Python transpiler project that targets C++ instead of Fortran is Pythran [10], which pyccl also refers to in benchmarks.

A related area of research is Python-like high performance languages such as mojo [11], which is not transpiled, but instead compiles to various native code targets including GPUs. The Julia language [12], which is increasingly utilized in HPC contexts, also has simple syntax compared to Fortran and is JIT-compiled for performance. FortScript offers advantages relative to both Fortran transpilers and standalone languages: it has much better parallelism support than existing transpilers, and also offers scientific computing developers the ability to modernize existing Fortran codes and take advantage of existing expertise while rapidly prototyping with high-level syntax.

Figure 1: 3D y^+ ([13] sect. 3.4.2) cell values extracted near the body's surface in ParaView from a FortScript Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) example.

3 Modern Fortran Parallelism

FortScript targets two forms of parallelism included in modern Fortran standards: loop-level `do concurrent` parallelism, and SPMD distributed parallelism. An excellent introduction to modern parallel Fortran can be found in [14]. An example parallel loop is shown below:

```
do concurrent (i = 1:n) local(tmp) reduce(+:total)
  tmp = a(i) * c(i)
  b(i) = tmp + d(i)
  total = total + tmp
end do
```

The loop above highlights several `do concurrent` features targeted by FortScript. One such feature is the basic data parallelism itself, where threads are automatically assigned to different indices i . Another is locality specification, which allows independent per-index variables to be created. Finally, a reduction specifier stores the results of a parallel sum in a thread-safe manner. It is worth noting that any methods called within a `do concurrent` loop must be *pure*, which is handled automatically by the FortScript transpiler [15].

FortScript also targets Fortran’s SPMD coarrays, which are a syntax extension allowing for parallel computation either on a single node with multithreading, or across an HPC cluster with multiple nodes. Coarray functionality is similar to MPI [2], allowing for distributed-memory parallelism [16]. As a syntax extension, coarray Fortran often results in more readable code compared to MPI. A simple coarray example is shown below:

```

real :: a(4,4)[3,*]
real :: x

a = real(this_image())

sync all

x = a(2,3)[1,2]

```

A copy of the program runs on each image (analogous to an MPI rank/worker), with the current image number exposed through the `this_image` function. A 4x4 array `a` is local to each image, with the square brackets `[3,*]` declaring the *codimensions* for access to images’ `a` data. In this example, `a` has *corank* 2, and the first codimension has *extent* 3. The extent of the second codimension is determined at runtime from the total number of images. Multiple codimensions allow programmers to naturally map parallel ‘neighbors’ in the problem at hand directly to the code. For instance, two codimensions can map to matrix block operations, while six codimensions could map to the six-sided blocks of a decomposed 3D finite volume mesh. MPI can, of course, achieve the same problem-mapped parallelism with slightly more bookkeeping code. Note that *coindices* (like `[1,2]`) are mapped to image number with column-major ordering.

Although coarrays as a simple `[...*]` syntax extension are useful by themselves, the Fortran 2018 standard introduced *collective routines* to further empower coarray users [17]. The following collective operations are supported by FortScript:

- `co_sum`: Collective summation
- `co_min`: Collective minimum
- `co_max`: Collective maximum
- `co_broadcast`: Collective broadcast (value of a coarray `A` on an image is assigned to `A` on all the other images)

There are more coarray features (teams, atomic operations, etc.) [5, 6] that have not been implemented in FortScript yet, but are on the roadmap.

4 Implementation

OCaml has a long history of usage for programming language research [18], and FortScript builds on that legacy. The transpilation process is as follows:

1. Lexing with `ocamllex` [19]
2. Parsing to an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) with `menhir` [20]
3. Semantic analysis
4. Code generation and builtin lowering

A single lexer source file provides a short specification of how `ocamllex` should perform tokenization. Next, the parsing stage is performed using `menhir`, and imports from outside FortScript files are handled before parsing. Semantic analysis is broken into several stages for typing, function calls, parallelism, and usage of keyword builtins. The final stage, code generation, walks the validated AST to emit a combination of straightforward substitutions and injected Fortran helper routines (for LAPACK [21] calls, plotting functionality, etc.) into a single Fortran source file. In general, the FortScript support library is bootstrapped, but compile-time text substitution into premade Fortran templates is used. Compilation of the generated Fortran code is done with `gfortran` for serial and/or `do concurrent` code, while compilation of coarray Fortran is done with the OpenCoarrays [22] compiler wrapper `caf`.

5 GPU Acceleration

FortScript also has experimental support for GPU acceleration using the NVIDIA Fortran compiler [23]. Parallel `do concurrent` loops are compiled separately using `nvfortran` and then linked to by the `gfortran`-compiled main program. This approach incurs some overhead due to data copying and potentially avoidable GPU (re)allocations, but it may be possible to reduce this overhead by using pinned memory as in [24].

6 FortScript Syntax Overview

FortScript syntax is intentionally similar to Python. Since FortScript is a DSL targeted at numerical computing, functionality and syntax from the popular NumPy [25] and Matplotlib [26] libraries are included in the language. A subset of the example program (*examples/slicing.py*) is included below:

```
# Array slicing demo

def extract_block(grid: array[float, :, :]) -> array[float, :, :]:
    block: array[float, :, :] # Mixed 2D slice
    block = grid[1:3, 1:4]
    return block

def main():
    grid: array[float, :, :] # Source matrix
    row: array[float, :] # Mixed index and slice
    col: array[float, :] # Mixed slice and index
    block: array[float, :, :] # 2D slice result

    grid = reshape(linspace(1.0, 16.0, 16), [4, 4])
    grid[1:3, 0:2] = 0.0 # 2D slice assignment
    row = grid[2, :]
    col = grid[:, 1]
    block = extract_block(grid)

    print("row[2]:", row[2])
    print("col[1]:", col[1])
    print("block[1, 1]:", block[1, 1])
```

That FortScript code results in the following generated Fortran code. Note that Python-like 0-based indexing is mapped to Fortran's default 1-based indexing, and that `linspace` is mapped to a Fortran implied-do array constructor:

```
function extract_block(grid) result(fortscript_result__)
    implicit none
    real(8), intent(in) :: grid(:, :)
    real(8), allocatable :: fortscript_result__(:, :)
    real(8), allocatable :: block(:, :)

    block = grid(2:3, 2:4)
    fortscript_result__ = block
    return
end function extract_block

subroutine main()
    implicit none
    real(8), allocatable :: grid(:, :)
    real(8), allocatable :: row(:)
    real(8), allocatable :: col(:)
    real(8), allocatable :: block(:, :)
```

```

integer :: fortscript_i__

grid = reshape([(1.0d0 + (16.0d0 - 1.0d0) * dble(fortsript_i__) / dble(16 - 1)), &
  fortsript_i__ = 0, 16 - 1]), (/ 4, 4 /))
grid(2:3, 1:2) = 0.0d0
row = grid(3, lbound(grid, 2):ubound(grid, 2))
col = grid(lbound(grid, 1):ubound(grid, 1), 2)
block = extract_block(grid)
write(*, *) "row[2]:", row(3)
write(*, *) "col[1]:", col(2)
write(*, *) "block[1, 1]:", block(2, 2)
end subroutine main

```

Key differences between Python and FortScript are as follows:

- Recursion is not permitted
- Type annotations are required
- Classes are not supported, but structures are (see below)
- Curly braces are used for coarray indices
- There are additional keywords and decorators for:
 - Fortran parallelism (next section)
 - Built-ins like array allocation, printing, etc.
 - Support library functionality
- General file I/O is not implemented, **but** HDF5/XDMF I/O for arrays and scalars is

An example of FortScript user-defined types (i.e. structures), which can be nested, is shown below:

```

struct Vec3:
  x: float
  y: float
  z: float

struct Body:
  pos: Vec3
  vel: Vec3
  mass: float

```

7 FortScript Syntax for Fortran Parallelism

FortScript exposes both forms of Fortran parallelism through lightweight syntax annotations. Loop-level parallelism is requested by placing an `@par` decorator immediately above a `for` loop, which the transpiler lowers to a Fortran `do concurrent` construct. Additional stacked annotations give fine-grained control over locality and reductions: `@local(...)` and `@local_init(...)` map to native Fortran 2018 `LOCAL` and `LOCAL_INIT` locality specifiers [15], while `@reduce(op: var)` is implemented via per-iteration scratch arrays that are combined sequentially after the loop, working around the current lack of native `REDUCE` clause support in `gfortran`. Functions called inside a `@par` body are automatically marked `pure` by the transpiler through a transitive call-graph analysis, satisfying Fortran’s purity requirement for `do concurrent`. An example parallel loop with locality and reduction annotations is shown below:

```

@par
@local(tmp)
@reduce(add: total)
for i in range(n):

```

```

tmp = a[i] * c[i]
b[i] = tmp + d[i]
total += tmp

```

SPMD distributed parallelism is expressed through coarray type annotations and image-access syntax. A scalar or array variable is declared as a coarray by appending `*` to its type, and remote image data is accessed using curly-brace indexing (`shared{img}`). Multiple codimensions, declared with additional bracket groups after the `*`, allow programmers to map a multi-dimensional process topology directly to the type system. For example, a 2D block decomposition can use `array*[float, :][:]`, which lowers to an allocatable Fortran coarray with two codimensions. Synchronization uses the `sync` keyword, and the Fortran 2018 collective operations `co_sum`, `co_min`, `co_max`, `co_broadcast`, and `co_reduce` are available as builtins [17]. The two parallelism models can be combined: a coarray program may contain `@par` loops for node-local thread parallelism, mirroring the common MPI+OpenMP pattern in HPC codes.

A minimal coarray example (*examples/coarray_hello.py*) is shown below:

```

def main():
    # Query the current image using FortScript's 0-based builtin.
    me: int = this_image()
    np: int = num_images()
    print("Hello from image", me, "of", np)

    # Scalar coarrays use the '*' suffix on the element type.
    shared: float* = 0.0

    if me == 0:
        shared = 42.0

    sync

    # Remote image access uses 0-based image ids in curly braces.
    val: float = shared{0}
    print("Image", me, "sees shared =", val)

```

8 Support Library

FortScript includes a support library which supplies users with functions and data types covering the following areas:

- Dense linear algebra
- Sparse linear algebra
- Optimization
- Parallel-safe random number generation
- 3D surface meshes
- 3D hierarchical Cartesian volume meshes
- 3D Finite Volume Method (FVM) functions [13]

The support library is largely bootstrapped, and as such it provides FortScript users with examples of how to write FortScript code. Some support modules build on each other (for instance: the FVM library uses the sparse linear algebra functionality). One of the included examples showcases the FVM support library by showing how to implement the PIMPLE algorithm ([27] sect. 5.21) for incompressible flow. A key enabler for the demonstration is the set of functions for (Cartesian) mesh refinement near the body's surface, which utilizes a Signed Distance Field (SDF) [28]. Some ParaView screenshots assessing the simulation results are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 1.

Figure 2: ParaView slice of the velocity magnitude field from a FortScript CFD example.

The simulation takes roughly three hours to complete on a 20-core machine for about three million cells and 500 timesteps. The CFD example above serves as powerful motivation for the usage of FortScript in scientific computing applications (in addition to the benchmarks in the following section). The FVM support library will be expanded in multiple ways as the project continues, including:

- Verification and Validation (V&V)
- Wall functions ([27] sect. 7.5)
- The $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model [29]
- Compressible flow
- Composition of loop-level and image parallelism
- Time-stepping improvements

A drop-in replacement for the `@par` loop annotation, `@omp` is sometimes utilized in the support library. This decorator uses OpenMP [1] for loop-level parallelism instead of `do concurrent`, which can be helpful since OpenMP loops do not have the same strict dependency analysis and purity requirements that the `do concurrent` loops (as implemented by gfortran) do. The FortScript transpiler performs some semantic analysis checks for basic race conditions with `@omp` in addition to some automatic variable locality specifier insertions. Users are encouraged to use `@par` when possible since it is more conservative; data races are much harder to produce with gfortran `do concurrent`.

9 Quality Control and Benchmarks

Three kinds of testing are carried out to ensure code quality in the FortScript repository:

- Unit tests (in the *tests* directory)
- Examples (in the *examples* directory)
- Benchmarks (in the *benchmarks* directory)

Unit tests are run with a shell script tallying up test passes and failures before versioning. Since the examples are generally more complex, they are run manually with outputs also manually verified. Output from one of the examples, a percolation simulation using the burning method, is shown in Figure 3. This example demonstrates FortScript’s integration with matplotlib for generating plots.

Figure 3: Percolation example outputs, with no percolation (left) and percolation achieved (right).

The included benchmarks shown in Figure 4 have two purposes: to demonstrate parallelism speedups offered by FortScript, and verify the correctness of the emitted FortScript code by comparing against known simulation results.

Figure 4: FortScript Benchmarks

The benchmarks in Figure 4 were performed with Ubuntu 26.04 inside a Docker container with an M3 Ultra CPU, with 20 threads/images used for parallel operations. The shallow water equations [30] benchmark solves a 2D finite difference problem using a predictor-corrector method on a 16,000x16,000 grid. The Ising benchmark runs a 3D Ising model simulation using Glauber (heat bath) dynamics on 134 million spins, with key statistics checked against known values [31]. The 3D molecular dynamics benchmark is adapted from pyccel [9], with the baseline Python code made faster using more idiomatic NumPy in order to provide a fairer comparison between Python and serial FortScript. 20,000 particles are simulated.

In the shallow water equations benchmark, serial FortScript is 9x faster than the NumPy baseline, with the `do concurrent` parallelized version at 15x faster. However, the `coarray` version of the shallow water benchmark showcases FortScript’s parallel capabilities well with a 31x performance increase. The 3D Ising Model benchmark shows equal parallel speedup of 12x with both loop-level and SPMD paral-

lelism. The 3D molecular dynamics benchmark shows FortScript loop-level parallelism outperforming the SPMD-style version. In all of the benchmarks, serial FortScript faster than NumPy. Having two modes of parallel programming available gives developers more flexibility when parallelizing their FortScript code.

Releases in the code repository use semantic versioning, with every release also including a changelog. Users are encouraged to open GitHub issues to obtain support for the software, including asking questions about setup, reporting bugs, or requesting features.

10 System Requirements

The recommended OS for FortScript is Ubuntu 26.04 (amd64 or arm64), either bare-metal or containerized (e.g. with Docker). Containerization is preferred, as the included container specification and dependency installation script provide a quick setup for new users. Containerization also allows for running the software on macOS, Windows, and a variety of Linux distributions. Although Docker is sufficient for single-machine setups, in distributed HPC contexts Apptainer [32] is recommended as it provides networking and performance enhancements.

The software has been tested with the following programming languages:

- OCaml 5.4.1 and 4.13.1 (any OCaml v4+ should be compatible)
- Fortran 2018
- Bash
- Python 3.12-3.14

A versioned shell script is included in the FortScript repository that handles building and installing the dependencies described below. Using Ubuntu 26.04 (optionally within a container) simplifies dependency management, which was previously done with `brew` and `conda`.

FortScript requires gfortran version ≥ 15.2 and < 16 , along with the following dependencies included as archives and built from source:

- OpenCoarrays [22] 2.10.3 or higher
- pyplot-fortran [33]
- h5fortran [34]
- prand [35]

Other dependencies are managed with `apt`:

- MPICH [36]
- opam [37]
- dune [38]
- fpm [39]
- cmake
- HDF5 [40]
- zlib

If GPU acceleration is desired, the NVIDIA HPC Toolkit [23] is required; version 25.5 or higher tested. GPU testing was done with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 mobile and CUDA 13.

11 Concluding Remarks

The reuse potential for FortScript is high: the software allows HPC application developers to leverage modern Fortran parallelism with a high-level syntax. The most obvious research areas in which FortScript could have an impact involve simulations (computational fluid dynamics, numerical weather simulation, cellular automata, etc.). FortScript could be used as a language in its own right to implement these simulations, act as a way to generate scaffolding for parallel Fortran software, and/or allow groups already utilizing Fortran to generate new parallelized functionality that can be integrated with existing codebases. FortScript is open-source and available on GitHub:

- Name: FortScriptTranspiler
- URL: <https://github.com/ianfr/FortScriptTranspiler>
- Licence: GPL 3.0
- First Public Release: April 04 2026

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